

SURVEY FOR SEX WORKERS

Hello. Thank you for participating in this survey. We are a team of researchers from the University of Lausanne and the Haute école of social work and health from Lausanne and we are interested in your experience during the coronavirus pandemic in Switzerland, since around March 1, 2020. **Please answer as honestly as possible, because there are no incorrect answers and your data will remain anonymous.**

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary and without remuneration. Likewise, all the data you provide is anonymous and confidential. If you would like to know more about this project, you can contact us by telephone by dialing 021 692 46 44 or by writing an e-mail to lorena.molnar@unil.ch

INTRODUCTION

0. For the last 12 months, have you performed sexual services in exchange for money, presents or services (prostitution/sex work)?

- Yes
- No

1. Your assigned sex (at birth) is:

- Female
- Male
- Intersex

2 You consider yourself as (gender):

- Woman
- Man
- Fluid gender
- Other

3. What is your age? _____

4. Do you have children? Yes No

5. Are you in a relationship or married? Yes No

6. Since March 2020, where have you lived (even if temporarily)? (Multiple replies possible)

- At your place
- At someone else's home
- At a erotic massage salon
- At a night shelter
- At a hotel
- On the streets
- Other _____

7. Since March 2020, have you had a Internet connexion in the place where you live?

- Yes, you have a Wi-Fi connexion where you live (pass to the question 8).
- Yes, you have an Internet subscription on your telephone (pass to the question 8).
- No, you have no Internet connexion (go to the question 9).

8. Since March 2020, you would say that your Internet connexion (Wi-Fi and telephone):

- It is a good connexion that almost ever goes down.
- It is a connexion that sometimes goes down.
- It is a bad connexion that almost always goes down.

9. You feel:

- Very unhealthy
- Unhealthy
- Neither unhealthy nor healthy
- Healthy
- Very healthy

10. Are you at a higher risk from coronavirus?

- Yes, you have health issues (immunological, respiratory problems, diabetes, etc.)
- Yes, you are a person aged 65 or more
- No

11. How has the pandemic affected your life (since March 1, 2020)? Select the answer which best applies to you.

Very negative impact	Negative impact	Neither a negative nor a positive impact	Positive impact	Very positive impact
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12. Since March 2020 to June 2020, where have you spent most of the time? (Multiple replies possible)

- In Switzerland.
- In your home country.
- In another country.

13. Since June 2020, where have you spent most of the time? (Multiple replies possible)

- In Switzerland.
- In your home country.
- In another country.

14. More into detail, since the beginning of the pandemic in Switzerland: (Multiple replies possible)

- You had to stop meeting friends/members of your family for a while
- You had to spend all or a large part of your savings
- You had to eat less for financial reasons
- You have lost your housing
- You applied for an allowance for loss of earnings for the self-employed
- You applied for the social help
- You applied for financial help from Fleur de Pavé, Caritas, church, etc.
- You asked for food vouchers from Fleur de Pavé, Caritas, church, etc.
- You asked for parcels from Fleur de Pavé, Caritas, church, etc.
- Your health got worse
- You have caught the coronavirus and had rather mild symptoms
- You have caught the coronavirus and had rather severe symptoms

15. If you have applied for an allowance for loss of earnings for the self-employed, how did you apply for this help?

- You applied for it by yourself.
- You applied for it, assisted by Fleur de Pavé.
- You applied for it, assisted by your close ones or acquaintances.
- You asked for it, assisted by the Social Service.
- Other (specify): _____

16. If you have received an allowance for loss of earnings for self-employed, how much monthly money have you received?
 _____ Swiss francs

17. Select the answer which best applies to you:

17.1 During the pandemic, you generally felt...

- Very unhappy
- Unhappy
- A bit unhappy
- Neither unhappy nor happy
- A bit happy
- Happy
- Very happy

17.2 During the pandemic, you have been anxious...

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

17.3 During the pandemic, you have been irritated...

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

YOUR LIFE FROM MARCH 2020 TO JUNE 2020

18. From March to June 2020, which have been your most important needs?
(Answer freely)

18.1 From March to June 2020, have you lived in the erotic massage salon where you worked at the moment of the prohibition of prostitution?

- Yes No

18.1.1 If YES, the life conditions were:

- Very good
- Rather good
- Not good nor bad
- Rather bad
- Very bad

Could you give two examples of your life conditions?

18.1.2 If YES, have you paid a rent? Yes No

18.1.3 If YES, has your rent increased since June 2020?

- No Yes You did not stay in an erotic massage salon from June.

19.1 From March to June 2020, you have spent the day, in person:

- Alone
- With strangers
- With friends
- With your significant other
- With family

19.2 From March to June 2020, you have interacted with friends or family from a distance (via social networks, WhatsApp, telephone, SMS, etc.):

- Every or almost everyday
- Several days each week
- Sometimes
- Never
- You do not have either family or close friends

20.1 From March to June 2020 (several replies possible)

- You had sexual intercourse in exchange of money
- You provided erotic webcam services
- You provided erotic telephone services
- You did not work in prostitution
- Other: _____

20.2 From March to June 2020, you performed sexual services (several replies possible):

- Via the Internet
- Via telephone
- In the street
- In an erotic massage salon
- At your place
- At the client's place, in the same locality where you live
- At the client's place, in another locality
- You did not work in prostitution.

21.1 From March to June 2020, have clients contacted you for performing sexual services face-to-face? Yes No

21.1.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

21.2 From March to June 2020, have clients insisted that you perform sexual services face-to-face? Yes No

21.2.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

YOUR LIFE SINCE JUNE 2020

22. Since June 2020, which have been your most important needs? (Answer freely)

23.1 Since June 2020, you have spent the day, in person:

- Alone
- With strangers
- With friends
- With your significant other
- With family

23.2 Since June 2020, you have interacted with friends or family from a distance (via social networks, WhatsApp, telephone, SMS, etc.):

- Every or almost everyday
- Several days each week
- Sometimes
- Never
- You do not have either family or close friends

24. Since June 2020 (several replies possible)

- You had sexual intercourse in exchange of money
- You provided erotic webcam services
- You provided erotic telephone services
- You did not work in prostitution
- Other: _____

25. Since June 2020, you performed sexual services (several replies possible):

- Via the Internet
- Via telephone
- In the street
- In an erotic massage salon
- At your place
- At the client's place, in the same locality where you live
- At the client's place, in another locality
- You did not work in prostitution

YOUR LIFE DURING THE PANDEMIC (SINCE MARCH 2020)

26.1 Since March 2020, have more clients than usual insisted that you decrease your tariffs? Yes No

26.1.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

26.2 Since March 2020, have more clients than usual insisted that you perform sexual services without a condom ? Yes No

26.2.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

26.3 Since March 2020, have your clients insisted that you perform sexual services without a facial mask ? Yes No

26.3.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

26.4 Since March 2020, have your clients insisted that you get tested for coronavirus ? Yes No

26.4.1 If YES, how many clients ? _____

26.5 Since March 2020, what helped you the most to face the pandemic ?

27. Compared to before the pandemic, do you consume more or less:

27.1 Tobacco

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- You do not consume

27.2 Alcohol

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- You do not consume

27.3 Drugs (cannabis, cocaine, heroin, etc.):

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- You do not consume

28. Since March 2020, have you been the victim of one of these actions?

	INDICATE WITH AN X IF THIS HAPPENED TO YOU	HOW MANY TIMES ?	WHERE ?	WHEN ?	COMPLAINED TO THE POLICE ?
A client did not pay you for the sexual service			<input type="checkbox"/> At home <input type="checkbox"/> In a hotel <input type="checkbox"/> In an erotic massage salon <input type="checkbox"/> In the street <input type="checkbox"/> In night shelter <input type="checkbox"/> At someone else's place <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Around the morning (between 6 a.m. and noon) <input type="checkbox"/> Around the afternoon (between noon and 6 p.m.) <input type="checkbox"/> Towards the evening (between 6 p.m. and midnight) <input type="checkbox"/> At night (between midnight and 6 a.m.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
You needed to go to another city but the client did not show up for the appointment			<input type="checkbox"/> At home <input type="checkbox"/> In a hotel <input type="checkbox"/> In an erotic massage salon <input type="checkbox"/> In the street <input type="checkbox"/> In night shelter <input type="checkbox"/> At someone else's place <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Around the morning (between 6 a.m. and noon) <input type="checkbox"/> Around the afternoon (between noon and 6 p.m.) <input type="checkbox"/> Towards the evening (between 6 p.m. and midnight) <input type="checkbox"/> At night (between midnight and 6 a.m.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Someone stole something from you like a wallet, money, phone, etc			<input type="checkbox"/> At home <input type="checkbox"/> In a hotel <input type="checkbox"/> In an erotic massage salon <input type="checkbox"/> In the street <input type="checkbox"/> In night shelter <input type="checkbox"/> At someone else's place <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Around the morning (between 6 a.m. and noon) <input type="checkbox"/> Around the afternoon (between noon and 6 p.m.) <input type="checkbox"/> Towards the evening (between 6 p.m. and midnight) <input type="checkbox"/> At night (between midnight and 6 a.m.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Someone hit you			<input type="checkbox"/> At home <input type="checkbox"/> In a hotel <input type="checkbox"/> In an erotic massage salon <input type="checkbox"/> In the street <input type="checkbox"/> In night shelter <input type="checkbox"/> At someone else's place <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Around the morning (between 6 a.m. and noon) <input type="checkbox"/> Around the afternoon (between noon and 6 p.m.) <input type="checkbox"/> Towards the evening (between 6 p.m. and midnight) <input type="checkbox"/> At night (between midnight and 6 a.m.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Someone assaulted you sexually by imposing you by means of force or threatens sexual practices which you did not wish to do			<input type="checkbox"/> At home <input type="checkbox"/> In a hotel <input type="checkbox"/> In an erotic massage salon <input type="checkbox"/> In the street <input type="checkbox"/> In night shelter <input type="checkbox"/> At someone else's place <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Around the morning (between 6 a.m. and noon) <input type="checkbox"/> Around the afternoon (between noon and 6 p.m.) <input type="checkbox"/> Towards the evening (between 6 p.m. and midnight) <input type="checkbox"/> At night (between midnight and 6 a.m.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

30. Currently, how much money, more or less, do you make each month?
_____ Swiss francs

31. Currently, how much cash, more or less, do you have in total? (In your pocket and/or in a bank account): _____ Swiss francs

32. If you had a magic wand, what would be the first thing you would do with it? (Answer freely)

33. What is the highest level of education you completed?

- You have no education
- Primary school (around 6 years of school completed)
- Middle school (around 9 years of school completed)
- High school or equivalent (around 12 years of school completed)
- University, polytechnic school, or higher education school (Bachelor, Master and/or PhD degree levels)
- Other (specify): _____

34. What is/are your nationality/nationalities? _____

35. Currently, in relation to sex work:

- You are not declared to the authorities as a sex worker
- You are Swiss and declared as self-employed
- You made the 90-day announcement for foreigners from the European Union
- You have an independent B permit
- You have an independent C permit
- Other: _____

36. If you are declared as a sex worker... were you also declared before the pandemic? Yes No

Use this box if you have additional comments:

Well done, you have finished the questionnaire! Your answers are precious to us and we hope that they will help in better taking care of you in the event of a future crisis. We thank you for your participation.